

On the Role of Irrotational Flow in Hydrodynamical Derivations of the Schrodinger Equation

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In (1), the Schrodinger equation is derived using a hydrodynamical continuity of density approach. Thus, spatial density represents x probability. There, however, is also a flow velocity field in the problem $v(x)$ and it is assumed this is irrotational. From this it is stated in (1) that $v(x)$ is proportional to $1/m \, d/dx \, S(x)$ ((1)) where $S(x)$ is some function and m is mass.

In this note, we argue that a particle moving in one dimension with constant p (momentum) is automatically irrotational, but it should satisfy ((1)) from (1). In other words, a constant p particle hence constant velocity is associated with a function of x , $S(x)$ even though its density in space is not. If one considers $S(x)=\ln(B(x))$, then ((1)) is equivalent to: $p = d/dx \ln(B(x))$. If one tries to associate $B(x)$ with a probability, then $\ln(B(x))$ is information = px . $B(x)$, however, is a different kind of x probability from density(x) which should be constant for a free moving particle. In fact, using $-id/dx$ instead of d/dx and $\exp(ipx)$ for $B(x)$, one finds $\exp(ipx)$ as a second x probability. Its modulus yields the constant value of density(x).

Thus the irrotational flow assumption leads to $p = dS/dx$. Incidentally, this form is equivalent to Fermat's least time principle for light with $p=p$ (x component). We argue that applying $p=dS/dx$ associates an x probability distribution even to a constant p , so the assumption $p=dS/dx$ is essentially a quantum mechanical statement, even if one does not derive the Schrodinger equation. The time independent Schrodinger equation may be obtained by using $\exp(ipx)$ as a relative probability and using energy conservation.

Continuity/Hydrodynamical Approach to Deriving Quantum Mechanics

In (1), the quantum Schrodinger equation is ultimately derived from a continuity/hydrodynamical view i.e.:

$$d/dt \text{ partial density}(x) = d/dx \{ \text{density}(x) v(x) \} \quad ((2))$$

Here $v(x)$ is a velocity field. It is assumed the velocity field is irrotational and it is argued that ultimately this leads to a form:

$$v(x) = 1/m \, dS/dx \quad ((3))$$

An immediate solution is: $S=px$, where px appears in the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ which is also the relativistic/nonrelativistic action written with $v=x/t$. Thus p becomes associated with the operator d/dx acting on a function and one ultimately sees this in the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

Fermat's Least Time Principle

We point out that Fermat's least time principle for light (reflection/refraction) minimizes the time that a straight light ray spends traveling from a starting point to a finishing one. The time may be recast in terms of distance using $d = c/n t$ where n is the index of refraction. Thus there is a function of x , $S(x)$ such that:

$$dS(x)/dx = 0 \quad ((4))$$

For reflection/refraction, there are two paths, one from the starting point to the mirror or medium interface and a second from this point to the final point. Thus:

$$dS(x)/x = dS1/dx - dS2/dx=0 \quad ((5))$$

((5)), however, is in the form of conservation law with $p(x$ component) being the conserved quantity. Here the mirror or the medium interface lies along the x -axis. In other words, associating an operator d/dx in Fermat's least time case, is not associated with irrotational flow in this example. Rather, a completely different idea is associated with d/dx being an operator which yields momentum.

Consequence of Irrotational Flow On a Constant Momentum

If one applies the idea of irrotational flow to a particle moving with constant p in one direction, motion is already irrotational, but:

$$p=dS(x)/dx$$

implies that there is an x function associated with the motion. This, we argue, implies a kind of x -probability, associated with the motion which allows for a constant p to emerge. $S=px$ is an immediate solution, but if one thinks in terms of information, one may write:

$$\ln(\text{probability}(x) = px \quad ((5))$$

((5)) leads to $S= \ln(\exp(px))$, but $\exp(px)$ grows indefinitely and so cannot be used. $\exp(ipx)$ with d/dx replaced by $-id/dx$, however, can.

Thus we suggest that the irrotational flow assumption leads to a new probability distribution $\exp(ipx)$ associated with constant p motion. This new probability is completely different from the probability= constant which would follow from spatial density, but $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = \text{constant}$. We argue that the assumption of irrotational flow, written as $mv(x)= dS/dx$ actually defines a main idea of the quantum mechanics of a free particle, namely that such a particle is associated with a probability $\exp(ipx)$.

As a result, the hydrodynamical approach seems to imply a velocity field $v(x)$, which if taken to be irrotational, implies $v(x)m = dS(x)/dx$ which in turn, applied to a free particle predicts the quantum mechanical probability $\exp(ipx)$.

Time-Independent Schrodinger Equation

Given the form $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability for a free particle with constant p , one may create an ensemble of weight $\exp(ipx)$ and calculate average kinetic energy at x . This average may then be used in a conservation of energy equation i.e.

$$KE_{\text{average}}(x) = \left\{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((6))$$

and $KE_{\text{average}}(x) + V(x) = E$ i.e. the time-independent Schrodinger equation ((7))

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that starting with a hydrodynamical/continuity equation approach to deriving quantum mechanics and assuming irrotational flow for $v(x)$, a velocity field, to mean: $v(x) m = dS(x)/dx$ ((8)) is equivalent to defining free particle quantum mechanics for a particle with constant p (momentum). In other words, the entire quantum features addressed arise from the assumption ((8)) which implies that a constant p (hence automatically irrotational) is associated with some function of x . This we argue means a probability in x when density(x) would be constant. For $p=\text{constant}$, $S=px$, or $\ln(\exp(ipx)) = ipx$. Using $-i\hbar d/dx$ instead of d/dx yields $\exp(ipx)$ as a quantum probability for a constant p particle. Using this to calculate average kinetic energy at x and adding to $V(x)$ before setting to E yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

References

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